

Challenges and Issues of Marketing

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Abstract

The complexity of development and growing and social change tensions between dominant results-based and emerging education and improvement-based ways of evaluating development attacks have created major challenges for the evaluation of communication for development (C4D). Drawing on our recent research, we identify significant tensions, issues and challenges in evaluating C4D. However, research in digital shopping and sustainability is very scarce. The purpose of this research is to examine the research on the subject, from 2009 until 2018, and to elaborate a research agenda about digital marketing and sustainability.

Introduction

Interest is one of the main drivers of the increasing gap between markets and companies. And one of the most important challenges for marketing. Digital marketing has transformed the way communicate and companies manage with their customers and society worldwide. It is becoming a key and necessary means to face the challenges that still exist in the field of marketing. At the same time, sustainability has transformed into one of the largest challenges for companies since the beginning of the 21st century, particularly for marketers. The discussion between marketing and sustainability has been generally treated by researchers, resulting in the fact that both concepts have common things to offer each other. Sustainability favours the gathering of improvements in the supply chain, the differentiation of stocks, access to aware investors, or a bigger commitment of the employees. In turn, marketing allows greater behavioural comprehension of the clients and a tool to influence society's attitudes and beliefs. This paper explores these and other tensions, issues and challenges related to the effective evaluation of C4D, drawing on our discussions with C4D and evaluation experts and other recent research. We propose a range of approaches to overcome these challenges and achieve more sustainable C4D outcomes then consider some policy implications.

The Current Development Evaluation Context

Implications for Assessing C4D the increasing complexity of the development setting since the 1990s poses significant new technical and methodological difficulties for development evaluation,

including the assessment of C4D. A broader vision of development centred on the Millennium Development Goals has developed, with a higher emphasis on effectiveness, targets.

This situation has led to increasing tensions between results-based (accountability) approaches, and emerging learning-based (improvement and effectiveness) approaches to evaluating development interventions (Army age 2011). In the former, impacts of complex interventions are often reduced to simple, cause-effect processes, using log frames, indicators that pre-determine impacts and outcomes, and methods that often priorities quantitative data. In participatory, contrast, systems and complexity-based approaches understand social change as emergent, unknowable, unpredictable in advance, something to learn from and adapt to, that may have contradictory or negative outcomes.

A good example of this new evaluation approach is outcome mapping which has shifted from a centre on assessing the impacts of a program (defined as changes in state such as reduced conflict) towards changes in relationships, behaviours, actions and activities of people, groups and organizations. This approach focuses on the more subtle changes that nevertheless “are clearly within a programme’s spheres of influence”.

Contentious debates are emerging about the limitations and challenges of increasingly dominant results-based management (RBM) approaches (Conlin and Stirrat 2008). Armytage suggests that until the challenges of development evaluation are asked: “there will remain a marked ‘evaluation gap’ between the theory and composition of the Paris Principles on Aid Effectiveness and the real world of expansion evaluation practice”. RBM and other upward accountability approaches have many limitations for evaluating C4D. This has significant implications for better policies and systems related to the implementation, planning and evaluation of C4D initiatives.

Tensions, Challenges and Issues in Evaluating C4D

Our research has identified many complex challenges, problems, tensions and contradictions in evaluating C4D. They are contextual, institutional, structural and organizational and affect the long-term sustainability and success of social change and development initiatives. Balit (2010a: 6) points out that both development and communication are political, and this is why “political will to put into a custom on the part of governments and local governments are often wanting. After all, allowing poor communities to participate directly issues existing power structures”. A similar argument can be made about the participation of a wide variety of people in the evaluation of C4D.

Contextual Challenges and Issues

They can significantly affect communication among evaluation participants and travel to making field research, research sites and data collection more time using and difficult. We experienced major news and travel problems in the AC4SC project due to the country’s wide cultural and linguistic diversity, high mountain terrain and poor ways, and short internet access outside the Kathmandu Valley. Ongoing political instability and discontent in Nepal often involved strikes that disrupted the transport network. These problems greatly affected field research work and participatory capacity development exercises, which involved program production and M&E staff from EAN and a network of community researchers based in various regions of Nepal.

Country and Institutional Level Challenges

Several significant barriers have affected the development and implementation of the UN’s C4D advocacy strategy, including its evaluation and capacity development strategies. Balit (2010a: 4) points out that C4D is a social process based on dialogue, it is a “soft and social science that has to do with hearing, building trust and serving local cultures – not easy concepts to understand for policy

makers and programme managers with a history in hard sciences”. This means that quantitative and continuing evaluation and planning approaches tend to dominate. However, as Balit (2010b: 2) notes, “counting and hard data cannot truly capture the complexity of social change processes over longer periods”. Our consultations found that some UN offices emphasise the use of quantitative approaches which are strange to provide the most meaningful and useful data on C4D results. One of the Expert Panel commented:

A key issue underlying the difficulties and challenges is that the M&E of C4D (like much other development) is typically approached in an upright, non-integrated manner, rather than being an integral part of programmes. An add on, for “M&E experts”. This reinforces the tendency towards top-down, “expert-driven” approaches and actively struggles against participatory methods (skills for which the former do not typically have).

Many organisational challenges also change the sustainability and effectiveness of the evaluation of C4D. One difficulty in planning and conducting evaluations of C4D was “The need for co-ordination between central HQ policy workers who want evaluations and field team for whom evaluation is an irritation”. Along with Puddephatt et al. (2009), members in our consultations for the UN Inter-agency Resource Pack emphasised the need for a long-term, sustained focus on potential development in evaluation for workers at all levels. However, they suggested that without the funding, understanding, support and commitment of senior UN directors and donors, changes to capacity and moves towards greater use of more innovative and participatory methods and systems are likely to be less successful.

Policies and Attitudes of Management and Funders

Senior managers and funders were seen as requiring an appreciation of the value and quality of both C4D and evaluation and managed not to support the use of more innovative or participatory approaches. One Expert Board member identified the following as a key challenge:

The opinions and biases of funders/those commissioning evaluation and research, combined with a lack of openness to less mainstream, less prescriptive more innovative, and predictable approaches. Both conceptually and in times of resourcing these processes, an unquestioning “more of the same” is all too commonplace, despite the suitability and fit with the aims of and values underlying the particular programme involved.

Such an assumption is reflected in the lack of adequate funding and resources provided for the evaluation of C4D. Byrne (2008: 4) highlights challenges with funding innovative evaluation practice in C4D and the frustrations of common at the field level with having to fit their achievements into externally imposed “SMART” objectives and log frames. Balit (2010a) also points to the problem of applying participatory processes within the rigid timeframes of log frames and RBM. Another issue is that evaluation studies often highlight successful C4D initiatives rather than those who were less successful but could provide valuable learnings, and lack of reporting on the long-term effects of communication programs (Puddephatt et al. 2009).

Challenges in Managing, Conceptualising and Preparing the Evaluation of C4D

Analysis of survey replies from our UN Inter-agency Resource Pack meetings identified a wide range of challenges in conceptualising, planning and managing the evaluation of C4D, some of which we have already noted:

Insufficient Funding, Time and Means

Comments on this Included

- Resources needed for research, if possible (which they are usually not) would be superfluous to the scale of the project/programme.

- Under resourcing the effort, requiring impact results from what is just “a drop in the ocean” case study.
- One UN respondent placed her most important challenge as “Finding the time to design evaluations for diverse programmes, where each requires specialised analysis”.
- Also, there was often pressure to “prove” results within a certain timeframe.

Low levels of Skills, Understanding, Capacity or Awareness of Research and Evaluation and Social Change

Comments Included

- Uneven understanding of behaviour and cultural change.
- Few skilled practitioners in many nations to conduct analysis, monitoring and evaluation of C4D.
- Weak capacity for evaluation and research ... and inadequate resources to restore nature at all levels, over a sensible timeframe.

Lack of Capacity to Design and Perform Research and Evaluation, and Lack of Useful Indicators or baseline Data

Issues Included

- Weak design of indicators, baseline learning, and conceptual approach to assessing the impact at the start of implementation.
- Evaluation is not imagined at the beginning of programmes.
- Diffuse, long-term and hard-to-measure effects expected from our schemes and programmes. Numbers are too difficult for field or local staff to apply.

Lack of Importance and Value were given to Research and Evaluation of C4D

Challenges Identified Included

- Convincing decision-makers and project directors that R, M & E of C4D is important.
- Low level of awareness among allies of nature and value of R, M & E for C4D.
- Lack of business among programmer governments, artists, other stakeholders in designs and use of evaluation results.

Attitudes to Evaluation Approaches, Methods and Processes

Challenges identified here indicated problems with the dominance of quantitative methodologies and giving scant attention to deeper evaluation issues. Comments included: To convince the contractor that quantitative methodologies will not provide the required data on how peoples’ lives changed. Only qualitative methodologies which allow people to participate and speak can store state information about social change. The apparent fascination with methods and tools, to the neglect of deeper, basic issues like Who is the evaluation for? What is it for? Who are the expected users of the evaluation? What are the intended uses? H

Challenges in Assessing the Forces and Outcomes of C4D

Although impact studies have in the past been pretty rare in development since they usually mean and time-intensive, they are now high on the development agenda. Inagaki (2007) identified a lack of published papers on high-quality impact assessments of C4D. Some of the challenges in demonstrating the impacts of C4D were aptly evaluated by one of the Authority

Panel Members in Our Consultations

Impact is a holy grail; it requires considerable funding and effort to gain credible results because information impact is challenging. It does not include latrines that have been built, it is about evaluating changes in how people think and react to issues and contexts, and this can be affected by many variables.

Argues that impact assessment of learning and communications for development (ICD) programs requires “sustained commitment on the part of implementing agencies, from plan design through to project completion and beyond”. He suggests that donors need to learn and be willing to recognise “that unexpected and even negative results need to be identified and understood; and that impact evaluation is not about the validation of past decisions but about the development of those that will be made in futurity” (Souter, 2008: 181).

Dominant approaches Alternative approaches Tensions and issues Dominance of effective, higher accountability-based approaches that focus on proving impacts, using linear cause-effect logic and formal reporting of results. Alternative approaches are not adequately resourced or maintained and are often critiqued for lacking ‘objectivity’, ‘rigour’ and ‘validity’. A flexible, holistic, interdisciplinary approach based on ongoing improvement, learning and understanding takes the complexity of social revolution and the particular context into account and focuses on outcomes that an initiative can realistically influence.

Demonstrating the impact of C4D is complex and difficult. Dominant approaches discourage ownership of the evaluation process and learning from the evaluation. Results are often biased towards positive issues, failures are not captured or learned from, and evaluations are not independent of donor influences. The pressure to deliver short-term results within rigid and unreliable timeframes. This results in a focus on more tangible, short-term moves that are not good indicators of long-term social change — seen as more important to focus on progress towards long-term social change and the contribution of C4D. This is a more realistic model of effectiveness and provides practical recommendations for the implementation of policies and initiatives. Longitudinal studies are required, but they are costly and one of the most profound challenges in evaluation. Donors are reluctant to fund them. This means that there is a lack of a strong mark on which to build C4D research, which fuels scepticism.

Attribution Problems

Attribution is deemed the “central problem” in impact evaluation (Leeuw and Vaessen 2009: 21). It is a key problem in assessing the impacts of C4D compared to some other development actions such as polio eradication programs where it can be easier to isolate changes in rates of the disease in a particular population. The effects and processes of communication can be difficult to measure. Balit (2010b: 1) suggests that in some instances, we can think about measuring changes in “knowledge, behaviour, emotions and access and use of services”. The problem of attribution remains, given the difficulty of attributing causality. Causality is difficult, and change is likely to be due to a whole variety of factors, which in turn act on each other.

Different factors may become relevant over time. It is often quite difficult to track and isolate those related to C4D. This is, in part, due to C4D often being a component of a larger development initiative that is usually undertaken in collaboration with several partner organisations and involves a range of media and community-based projects. This presents a particularly difficult test, because of the governments of aid, which means that implementing agencies are “often tempted to claim credit for forces because that is what those they are accountable to want to hear” (Souter 2008: 162).

The complexity of assessing the forces of C4D is highlighted by Inagaki (2007: 34-35): ... general categories such as mass media and interpersonal communication can potentially conceal varying effects among specific channels within each mode, such as one-to-one interpersonal contacts versus group discussion, simulcast media versus printed materials ... different communication channels interact with one another, and this interaction can form a complex network of communication effects encompassing multiple, direct and secondary paths of influence.

When measured alone, a mass media message may have negligible direct forces, but the same message can have significantly greater impacts when mediated through other channels of communication, such as interpersonal communication and group discussion. The value of conventional evaluation approaches that are based on a program remaining static during the evaluation method needs to be weighed against the benefits of giving the freedom and flexibility to C4D initiatives to continually change and respond to changing ideas, settings and environments and endless feedback. The idea of cause and impact and causal relationships is not very useful here.

Timeframe Issues

Our research identified unrealistic demands, targets and timeframes for the impact assessment process, with patrons expecting to see measurable results from C4D forces in an unreasonably short timeframe, most likely learned through measurable pre-set symbols. This can lead to the creation of “results” that may have little connection with activities on the ground. If social change is recognised as an emergent, ongoing and complex process, it becomes very difficult to understand and demonstrate the impact of a C4D drive through measurable pre-set symbols within a short timeframe. Impact assessment is usually undertaken immediately after the end of a project’s implementation. Social change is ongoing; results of interventions often lie in the future, beyond the immediate project (Souter 2008).

The main issues here are the timeframe of development funding and reporting demands based on dominant upward-accountability evaluation approaches. These two factors negatively impact the likelihood of success, as well as concepts of what constitutes success, and how its strength be demonstrated. In Inagaki’s (2007: 41) review of 37 studies on the impact of C4D programs, only four provided any evidence of long-term impacts, “and even among these studies results going beyond the immediate timeframe of the project are discussed through anecdotal accounts rather than systematic analyses”.

Project implementation timeframes are usually too short to be able to assess long-term impacts. The average time of funding for projects reviewed by Inagaki (2007) was two years, and over half of the 37 studied had an active project duration of one year or less. Parks et al. (2005) suggest that evaluating the meaning of Communication for Social Change businesses should look at the short-term, intermediate and long-term impact. While Skuse (2006: 25) looks out that understanding the behavioural result of radio programs is “particularly difficult and can just occur over the long-term”, he claims that “there is scope to set interim behaviour development notices within ICD programmes that can and should be evaluated”.

Souter (2008: 164) proposes that the best way of assessing “lasting and sustainable change” is to use longitudinal education “undertaken some time (six months, two years, five years) after project closure”. However, he notes that the objection of donors to fund such studies is a critical problem in cities like ICD “where there is no strongly confirmed evidence base of experience on which to build” (Souter 2008: 164).

Strategies to Overcome the Hurdles and Key Trends in C4D Evaluation

The following new conceptualizations of evaluation and changes in evaluation practice have significant implications for understanding and evaluating C4D

- Evaluation is seen as an ongoing learning and organizational improvement method.
- There is a shift from proving impacts to developing and improving initiatives.
- The use of evaluative processes to support the development of innovations.
- A shift from external to internal and community accountability (Lennie and Tacchi, 2013). These shifts respond in meaningful ways to the difficulties and issues outlined above and help to provide an environment for C4D evaluation practices that are presently supportive of better development planning and practice at all levels. For example, shifting to a greater focus on improvement highlights the value of focussing on progress towards long-term social change and the contribution made by C4D, as opposed to attempts to measure and attribute impact. Other key strategies that can help to overcome the challenges and issues identified above and achieve more sustainable C4D outcomes are outlined below.

Highlight the Value of Creative and Innovative Approaches to Evaluating C4D

A key finding from our UN consultations was that more openness, freedom and flexibility is needed in the selection and use of various evaluation methodologies, approaches and methods to ensure that they are appropriate and fit the aims of the C4D initiative. Innovative and creative participatory approaches, such as developmental evaluation (Patton 2011), ethnographic action research (EAR) (Tacchi et al. 2007) and the Most Important Change technique (Davies and Dart 2005), can foster new understandings of local problems, facilitate community engagement and dialogue and individual and population change. We consider these approaches highly relevant and effective for the evaluation of C4D.

Creative processes such as digital storytelling, drawing pictures and maps, and photovoice techniques are also important. They are frequently used in different stages of development research and evaluation as essential components of ethnographic and participatory action analysis methodologies (Liamputtong 2007; Rattine-Flaherty and Singhal 2009). The feminist Nicaraguan C4D foundation Puntos de Encuentro (Lacayo 2006), which used flexible and creative methods to achieve and evaluate its programs, is a good example of innovation, as is developmental evaluation, EAR and the participatory M&E approach used in AC4SC. All of these examples used mixed methods, innovative, participatory approach to research and evaluation.

Use a Rigorous Mixed Systems Evaluation Approach

Rules and complexity approaches highlight the need for methodological pluralism. Midgley (2006) notes that this is important to producing a flexible and responsive evaluation approach, which is required in the evaluation of C4D interventions. Our UN interviews found that 80% of UN respondents and 79% of Expert Panel respondents reflected a mixed-methods approach “very important” in their work. A pragmatic, mixed-methods approach can present a fuller and more realistic picture of social change, shed light on many issues, and increase the strength and rigour of evaluation findings. It can capture different perspectives, is suitable for exploring complex situations and problems, can help to provide detail about local connections, and can facilitate the collection of sensitive information and the inclusion of hard to reach groups (Bamberger et al. 2010).

A mixed-methods approach allows us to select from a broad range of methodologies and methods, producing exactly the kind of flexibility that is needed in the evaluation of C4D. While many development agencies have used mixed-method evaluations for several times, they have taken a somewhat ad hoc approach, and resources have normally not been available to increase their rigour

(Bamberger et al. 2010). A participatory, mixed-methods approach also requires a wider variety of skills and knowledge to use effectively than standard evaluation approaches. This highlights the need to improve capacities and resources to more effectively undertake mixed methods evaluations of C4D.

Implement Long-Term, Holistic Evaluation Capacity Development at All Levels

There are many benefits in strengthening capacities in evaluating C4D among staff and stakeholders at all levels. A holistic approach to evaluation capacity development can increase the sustainability of C4D organisations and initiatives. This is a long-term approach that focuses on the development of organisations as a whole, rather than individual staff members (Horton et al. 2003). It needs a shift in how both evaluation and potential development is approached and experienced. The aim here is to develop organisations that continuously learn from success and mistakes, improve their practices, respond effectively to complex and rapidly changing contexts, and incorporate local change and ideas into the process (Hay 2010; Horton et al. 20)

Institutionalising evaluation, receiving an evaluation culture within organisations at all levels, and building the evaluation capacities of staff and stakeholders improves the quality of the evaluation, knowledge about evaluation and its role in the learning process, and C4D design and outcomes. However, as Pearson (2011) found in her work on a long-term space development project in Cambodia, there are many challenges and points of resistance that need to be identified and overcome. Strategies for overcoming these challenges include empowering local workers and cities involved in development projects.

Implement our Recently-developed Framework for Evaluating C4D

Another key strategy for addressing the challenges and issues of evaluating C4D is to implement our framework for evaluating C4D (Lennie and Tacchi 2013; Tacchi and Lennie 2014). Given its open, flexible and pluralistic approach, it can help to bridge the divide between upward accountability and learning-based approaches to the evaluation of development initiatives (Lennie and Tacchi 2014). Our framework aims to assert and demonstrate the value, rigour and appropriateness of alternative approaches to evaluation. It is based on concepts and principles derived from systems and complexity theory, action research, feminist and gender-sensitive evaluation methodologies, new approaches to social change, and holistic approaches to community development, organisational change, and evaluation capacity development. These approaches promote ongoing learning from and continuous listening to a broad diversity of participants and stakeholders. This framework proposes ways of critically thinking about the evaluation of C4D and suggests how to go about it. It consists of seven key, inter-related components – participatory, holistic, complex, critical, emergent, realistic and learning-based and principles that inform each component.

The framework fits most comfortably within a holistic approach to development based on systems and complexity thinking, which is increasingly seen as important to the development and its evaluation (Miskelly et al. 2009; Ramalingam et al. 2008). It takes a participatory, flexible, mixed-methods approach to research and evaluation, and incorporates action learning and a critical, realistic, road to social change and evaluation. It advocates paying attention to power relations, a difference (such as gender, age, ethnicity and education levels) and social and cultural norms in the process of researching and evaluating C4D. It emphasises people, relationships, processes, and principles such as inclusion, open communication, trust and continuous learning. This approach can help to reinforce the case for effective two-way communication and dialogue as central and vital components of participatory forms of development and evaluation that seek positive social change.

Implications for C4D Policy

The challenges and issues outlined above have several significant policy implications for C4D and communication for social change. They include policies related to use of a broader range of evaluation approaches; providing sufficient time and resources for evaluations and evaluation capacity development; creating evaluation cultures within development organisations; and new understandings of accountability. More openness, freedom and flexibility is needed in the selection and use of different evaluation approaches, methodologies and methods to ensure that they are appropriate and match the appropriate aims of the C4D initiative (Byrne and Vincent 2011).

This requires a more open-minded approach to evaluation that draws on participatory and innovative methods that are more suited to the evaluation of C4D and can increase community inclusion, participation and empowerment. This process involves considering the strengths and limitations of all evaluation approaches, methodologies and methods, including participatory approaches. Addressing the difficulties and issues, we have identified also requires that those implementing C4D initiatives are given sufficient budgets and time for evaluation, including for longitudinal studies that identify expected, unexpected, positive and negative outcomes. There is a clear need for more supplies and support for evaluation capacity development at all levels, from grassroots to management.

This requires a holistic strategy that aims to develop learning organisations that continuously improve their M&E practices and capacities, and can contribute to improving effective policies, strategies and initiatives that better address complex development goals. While the leadership of senior management is important to promoting organisational change towards an evaluation culture, Raeside (2011: 101) stresses the importance of staff understanding their power to create money and the need to empower staff to act on the information they gain from constantly interacting with communities. Raeside (2011: 101) argues that “If these staffs are not empowered to act on this knowledge, it is unlikely that real power transformation will occur at this level, or that this information will ever trickle into mainstream development debates”. This implies that organisations need to empower local M&E and C4D staff to act on the knowledge, shrewdness and feedback obtained from their regular interactions with people at the community level, including those who could be great catalysts for social changes.

We have noted the recent change from evaluations being mainly based on upwards, external accountability to donors, to greater stress on internal, personal and downwards, community-level responsibility. David and Mancini (2011: 245) observe that over the last decade there has been an increased focus on responsibility to primary stakeholders, accompanied by experimentation with “participatory methods that address issues of power, authority and rights and open up new frontiers of enquiry, learning and understanding of change”. Likewise, Jones (2011: ix) comments on the development of innovative systems for feedback and increasing emphasis on transparency and accountability in development interventions. These new understandings of accountability have significant suggestions for evaluation reporting policies and practices in this field, including the business of effective two-way communication and feedback systems that can improve the success of participatory evaluations.

Conclusion

This paper has highlighted significant tensions, challenges and issues related to the effective and rigorous evaluation of C4D. We highlighted growing tensions between dominant results-based (upward accountability) approaches and emerging learning-based (improvement and effectiveness) approaches to evaluating development interventions. Our research has identified numerous contextual, structural and institutional challenges, issues and barriers, including problems with

communication, attitudes towards C4D and evaluation, and with conceptualising, training and planning the evaluation of C4D. We found a lack of skills and capacities in both evaluation and C4D, and a lack of appreciation, funding and assistance for alternative evaluation approaches that are more appropriate for the evaluation of C4D, compared with dominant RBM approaches. There are many challenges in assessing the impacts and outcomes of C4D, given the complexity of social change, difficulties with attribution and the unrealistic demands, targets and timeframes that are often imposed by donors. We proposed various strategies that can help to address these challenges and issues, including highlighting the value of creative and innovative approaches to evaluating C4D. This can be achieved through examples such as AC4SC and Puntos de Encuentro, which both applied a participatory, mixed methods, learning-based approach to program development and evaluation.